

Smart tutor to provide feedback in programming courses

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming more and more popular as time passes, allowing to perform tasks that were difficult to do in the past. From predictions to customization, AI is being used in many areas, not being educational environments outside this situation. AI is being used in educational settings to customize contents or to provide personalized feedback to the students, among others. In this scenario, AI in programming teaching is something that still has to be explored, since in this area we usually find assessment tools that allow grading the students work, but we can not find many tools aimed towards providing feedback to the students in the process of creating their program. In this work we present an AI based intelligent tutor that answers students programming questions. The tool has been tested by university students at the URJC along a whole course. Even if the tool is still in its preliminary phase, it helped the students with their questions, providing accurate answers and examples. The students were able to use the intelligent tutor easily and they thought that it could be a useful tool to use in other courses.

1 Introduction

Although the number of students in technical degrees grow each year, the number of teachers qualified to teach this type of degree is not (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, 2018). These degrees and even those who are less about technology, often have programming courses included in them. Therefore, many institutions are working to offer students resources to support them during the introduction to programming courses. To ease this support, there should be teachers able to give feedback to the students so they are able to assimilate the concepts taught during the teaching sessions.

Regarding computer programming, many of these sessions take place in a classroom with computers, where the students program the tasks given by their teachers. These sessions are fundamental for the students, since they can receive just-in-time feedback. However, the large number of students that usually attend a session, moreover in the university environment, makes it difficult for a teacher to provide individual and personalized feedback for each student(Song

et al., 2021). Programming skills, which are difficult to acquire and that are growing in importance in the last decade, requires extra dedication by both teachers and students, and each piece of feedback is fundamental (Qian and Lehman, 2017). In this scenario, to be able to solve any issues or doubts, we believe that it would be helpful to give the students an extra opportunities outside and inside the teaching sessions so they can receive feedback which is adjusted to their questions through the use of artificial intelligence.

Reviewing the literature, it is possible to find many studies about the automatic assessment of student's codes (Orr and Russell, 2021; Cardoso et al., 2021). Automatic assessment exists since 1960. However, we do not only want to focus in automatic assessment of the final result, but to provide feedback during the process of creating the final program. This is why it is not enough to provide a solution, but to provide more resources that will go beyond the development of that solution (Bayerlein, 2017). We consider that the goal would be to be able to redirect students towards the correct solution, without necessarily providing that solution.

Analysing the kind of feedback that is valuable to a student that is coding is not a trivial task. Some authors confirm that the most important part in the process is that the feedback must help the student to understand the cause of the mistake they made (Lohr and Berges, 2021). To do so, it is fundamental that the students understand the feedback. In most scenarios, a teacher pointing out an error does not imply that the student comprehends the cause of the error (Keuning et al., 2019).

When coding, some mistakes can be solved by reading and interpreting the messages offered by the compiler of the corresponding programming language. However, the information offered by the compiler is usually not understood by the students, so at the end they are unable to detect the mistake they made. In our work we want to offer a tool that is able to interpret the students' questions to offer automatic feedback that can be easily interpreted by the students. Not only the will be answered, but the tool will also provide several examples that represent the questions they make. The tool focus on the root of the errors rather than in the final solution offering detailed feedback about the cause of an issue. An initial prototype of the tool has been tested with students of the Programming Fundamentals course of the first year of the Biomedical Engineering Degree of the URJC in the 2022-2023 academic (1st semester).

2 Background

2.1 Automatic feedback

In educational settings, offering feedback to the students is essential in the teaching and learning processes since it helps students to identify mistakes and to evaluate their knowledge (Butler and Winne, 1995). The feedback should offered information related to the task done by the student, aiming to fill the existing gaps between the students' knowledge and the intended teaching goals

(Hattie and Timperley, 2007). In Henderson et al. (2019) work, 7 studies were presented, explaining the importance of designing the feedback processes.

There is plenty of empiric evidence that points out the interactive dialogue between teachers and student as an essential component of learning, taking also into account the pedagogic strategies used by the teachers in those dialogues (Ezegan and Boyer, 2013). Many researchers have tried to incorporate those strategies in their feedback systems, although those systems did not reach the level of human teachers (VanLehn, 2011).

When offering feedback, the literature identifies 2 types. Negative feedback, that is given when the student makes a mistake and positive feedback, in which the student solution is analysed and the teacher indicates if one of the steps followed toward the final solution was inappropriate (Di Eugenio et al., 2009). Human teachers provide these two types of feedback and several tools have been created in order to replicate it. However, more efforts were done in the area of negative feedback, which is easier to recognize automatically in a tool (Cavalcanti et al., 2021).

In this sense, we can find two ways of generating feedback. Reactive feedback given in answer to questions and actions carried by the students and proactive feedback, that addresses future concerns of the students in order to direct them before mistakes are made (Duke, 1991). In many scenarios, giving feedback after the student makes a mistake could be too late, since the student could have interiorized a wrong solution that could be difficult to modify (Gardiner, 2017).

When coding, a reactive feedback given once the task has been completed is not enough. This type of feedback, based on the final solution, is usually given by tools oriented to the functional evaluation of the students' code (Keuning et al., 2019). However, we believe that it is needed to give feedback about the process and to progress towards the solution if the student gets stuck. Some tools already offer feedback along the coding process, but they are centered in the solution offer by that tool, preventing the development of alternative solutions by students (Paolo et al., 2015).

To create a complete feedback system which is able of addressing the needs of the students it is fundamental to understand the students difficulties. Qian and Lehman (2017) identified and classified the difficulties and mistakes encountered by beginners programmers. Among them, we can find syntax errors, conceptual and strategic errors, and the different approaches to address those issues. Offering different feedback, detailing and using examples to explain the aforementioned areas, helps when offering effective feedback, following the same process a human teacher will follow (Keuning, 2019).

2.2 Natural language processing in coding

When a student writes code not only we need to pay attention to that code in order to offer feedback, but also to the students thoughts since many times the student questions about the different ways to solve a task and about if the idea he/she has thought about is the correct one. Being able of interpreting the

students' questions and generating dynamic feedback that can be usable is not a functionality that can be found in programming courses (Suciu et al., 2021).

For a computer to be able to understand the student, so it can generate appropriate feedback, it is necessary to use Natural Language Processing (NLP). This area of artificial intelligence (AI) aims to give the computers the ability of understanding words and sentences the same way as humans. NLP combines statistics, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). Through NLP it is possible to translate a text to another language, answer to commands, summarizing large texts or analysing the sentiment of a sentence, among others. In the last years there have been some efforts into the exploration of the potential of applying NLP in educational settings, being one of the most common tasks including NLP into the existing conversational tutors (Mathew and Paulose, 2021). However, there are not many examples of NLP used in programming courses.

When a student is coding, there are many occasions when the student has doubts, questions or simply does not understand why what you have programmed does not work as he/she expected. This kind of questions can not be solved with a reactive feedback based in the final solution of the student. At this point, doubts will remain and the student may have reached the correct solution by sheer luck (Shute, 2008).

We can find in the literature platforms such as Beetle II (Dzikovska et al., 2014), an intelligent tutor designed to teach physics. This tool uses NLP to give dynamic feedback combined with a curriculum that groups the best programming practices. It is possible to find other tutors that converse with students to guide them when solving a task, but those tutors do not use NLP to analyse the conversation with the student since it uses pre-programmed conversations aimed to solve a single activity, therefore, they can not be used in a generic way. One of these examples is ProPL (Lane and VanLehn, 2005).

In our work we want to create a tool that gives supports in the different problems that arise when students learn to program. As aforementioned, these issues can be summed up in syntax errors, conceptual and strategic errors. We use NLP to naturalize the way of offering feedback to the students during the process of creating the program, allowing the student to ask questions and doubts so the tool can give the student information to avoid bottlenecks or simply by helping the student in to make a decision. We believe that this second part has not been researched enough, since there are more efforts in the analysis of the students' final solution, and those solutions who work in the conversation with the students, are based in pre-programmed conversations without using NLP.

3 Research questions

With the main goal of testing if NLP helps students in introductory programming courses, we have developed a tool based in this technology to be able to offer dynamic feedback to students by means of conversation when they are cod-

ing their tasks. We believe that some of the main problems are the inability of students to interpret the compiler errors and how some conceptual errors that can be solved automatically with little explanation makes them to lose lots of their time (Infinite loops, simple syntax errors, variable initialization, etc). Our tool is centered in the process, rather than in the final solution given by the students. Therefore, the questions that we are addressing with this work are.

- Can artificial intelligence be used in programming courses to address students questions? Is the tool able to interpret correctly the students questions? The tool should be able to easily assess the students questions, since a wrong answer will confuse the student even more.
- Do the students feel that the tool really helps them? In order to assess this, the students will fill a questionnaire at the end of the course in order to give their impressions.
- Can the tool be applied to different scenarios? We intend to extend the tool to be able to address questions in many different scenarios.

4 Methodology

Our work has different phases. The first phases consisted of gathering the most common questions that the students of the Programming Fundamentals course made during the 2021-2022 academic year. Afterwards, we created a DL model trained with the data gathered in that first phase, so the tool could answer a students question. In this second phase, the tool will include functionality that will allow the student to interpret correctly the compiler messages, and functionality that will analyse the students current code to find inconsistencies. The model is not based in a complete dialogue model, since we need to focus on programming concepts rather than in general conversations. This way, the model will remain simple and we will be able to deploy it only so the tool can be accessed whenever, wherever.

Since the beginning of the programming course (September 2022) the students are able to access the tool in order to ask questions. The tool is based on a *chatbot* with which students can have conversations about the course. The tool was operative 24/7, meaning that the students can ask questions both in the teaching sessions and outside the teaching sessions. Not only programming questions are addressed with the tool, but also questions related to the course itself (timetables, contents of the course, date of the exam, etc). Not only the students can ask questions 24/7, but they will be also able to assess the answer given by the tool by pointing out if the answer was helpful or not.

At the end of the course, the students will fill a System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire in order to rate the tool usability and performance and to give their own textual opinions about the best things, worst things and how to improve the tool.

5 Architecture

The developed platform is composed of four components: The model, which will be used to interpret student questions and give the corresponding answer; the front-end, which is a React based *chatbot* that will act as the user interface for the student and; the back-end, which is an API written using Python that will receive the student inputs (questions and scores) and will manage them in order to generate an answer or to perform the corresponding task and; a Dash application, that will process the data generated by the platform and it will generate visualizations with that data. All this components use a MongoDB database in order to store and access the data generated by the platform and we have also developed some scripts to train and to test the model. In addition, we created several scripts in order to train, test and analyse the model that are used locally prior to uploading the definitive model to the web application. The architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Architecture of the platform

Although the main components are located in the server, both the training and testing of the model are done locally to avoid drops in performance in the server. The dataset used to train the model contains 15 different topics with 20 different ways of asking about each specific topic. The model is based on a Sequential DL model with 3 neural dense layers. The first layer is composed of 128 neurons, the second one is composed by 64 neurons and the third one is composed by 15 neurons, since that is the layer that will produce the output when predicting. The model uses a categorical cross-entropy loss function, and Stochastic Gradient Descent with a learning rate of 0.01. As an example, one

question could be "Why does my loop do not end?" and the model will interpret the intention of that question and it will generate the corresponding answer. The description of the model can be found in Fig. 2. — TO ADD —

As aforementioned, is a web-server where all of the main components of our platform will be deployed. First of all, there is a REACT base chat that is the component that allows a student to ask questions to the model. As shown in Fig. 2 the web application is composed of two separate components. The chat itself, where the student can write questions, receive answers and give scores to those answers (Left side) and a component where the examples related to those questions are shown (Right side).

The web application, once the student interacts with it, sends information to a REST API application written using the FastAPI module that has been developed with Python. The chat connects with the REST API in three different occasions: To register the activity in the chat, to send a question in order to receive an answer and to register the score given by the student to a certain answer. When registering the activity in the chat and when registering the score given to an answer, the REST API stores the generated information in a MongoDB database. When being asked a question, the REST API queries the corresponding model in order to generate an answer. This answer is sent back to the chat with the corresponding examples so everything is presented as shown in 2.

Figure 2: REACT chat.

In order to review the activity of the platform and the scores given by the

students, we designed a visualization dashboard with the module Dash which is written in Python. This first prototype shows two different types of graphs. In the first one, the total amount of questions asked, divided by the intention of that question, is shown. In the second graph, it is possible to see the scores that the students have given to the answers received. When asking a question and receiving an answer, the student can tell the application if the answer helped him/her, if it did not help him/her or if he/she just asked a random question that he/she knew beforehand that the platform will not be able to answer. Examples of these visualizations are shown in section 6.4.

6 Experimental validation

In this section we present a pilot study done with students at the URJC. The main goal was to assess the accuracy of the tool and the perceptions of the students. This study has enabled us to lay the foundations of the platform for using it in future academic years with more users. In addition, some relevant statistics from logged data about the platform usage of real students are briefly analyzed.

6.1 Research context and participants

Our platform has been used with 37 students in the 2022-2023 academic year. The students belong to the course *Programming Fundamentals* of the Biomedical Engineering Degree at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (URJC). The platform was available during the whole course, which lasted 14 weeks. The contents are the following: Variables and operations, if sentences, loops, functions, lists and tuples, exceptions, files and dictionaries and sets.

Each week, the students have a session of two hours where they have to solve through coding the programming exercises provided by the teacher. In this course, the students program with Python using Jupyter-Notebook, which allows a good combination between code and text explanations. During these sessions, the students code themselves and they come up with questions about the code they are writing.

Some of these questions are related to conceptual errors and even about the programming environment usage that can be solved just by following simple instructions that do not require much explanation. However, most of the questions are about these areas and they still require time to be explained. For instance, sometimes the kernel of Jupyter-Notebook breaks, which is solved by clicking a button in the menu. However, students sometimes do not find that button. These kind of errors can be solved without the assistance of a teacher. Other conceptual errors, such as not increasing nor decreasing the iterator in a loop, or not changing the condition that terminates a loop, are also errors that can be easily solved without the assistance of a teacher.

All these kind of mistakes the students make, consume some minutes in a 2 hour session. These leaves little time to solve questions that could be funda-

mentally more difficult to solve by a student without assistance. For instance, a question that is repeated many times in the laboratory sessions is, "who can I start working?". The main goal of the platform is to provide assistance for those 'minor' mistakes that can be solved easily without the teacher assistance while letting the teacher provide assistance in those matters that can not be solved automatically, optimizing the time usage in the laboratory sessions.

6.2 Research design

The main goal of this study was not to assess students' learning, therefore no evaluation was done in this regard. In future studies, we will compare the performance of groups who can use the online tutor with groups that are not able to use it. The main goal of the intelligent tutor is to provide extra assistance to the students so they are able to solve their doubts independently without needing to wait for the teacher to be available.

As aforementioned, the students used the platform during the whole course. They had to deliver weekly exercises starting from September 28th. They had 1 week to deliver each set of exercises. The platform was available 24/7.

In this scenario, the visualizations provided with Dash allows us to assess the activity of the students with the intelligent tutor. With this information, we are able to review the concepts most frequently asked about. Moreover, we can see at first glance, as it will be shown in section

6.3 Satisfaction questionnaire

At the end of the semester, the students were given a satisfaction questionnaire that they needed to complete for us to be able to assess the intelligent tutor usability. This questionnaire is based on the System Usability Scale questionnaire [2]

TOADD graphs

6.4 Preliminary analysis of real data

As aforementioned, the visualizations consist of two different graphs. In the first graph, it is possible to detect the most problematical issue that the students are asking about and, it will be also easy to detect those questions who did not receive an answer because the model could not find an appropriate answer. In this scenario, sometimes the reason of not finding an answer is because the question is not among the questions the model is prepared to answer. For instance, a student may ask about who is going to win the Champions League this year, and the model is not prepared to answer that. However, sometimes the model may not interpret correctly a perfectly valid question, so we would need to review the model and to retrain it adding more different ways of asking about the same topic. An example of a graph that shows how many questions of each intention have been asked is shown in Fig. 3.

There is a second graph that shows the scores given by the students to the answers that the intelligent tutor gave to them. This second graph show these scores, both generally and filtering by intention. An example of the total scores given by the students to the answers. If *Yes*, it means that the answer helped the student, *No* represents that the answer did not help the student and *I asked a random question* means that the student did not ask something related to the course. The visualization is shown in Fig. 4.

With the visualizations it is possible to follow the activity of the students along the course, being able to improve the intelligent tutor on the fly by adding new questions or new ways of asking about the same concept. Moreover, we are able to include more examples if the current ones are not enough to solve a particular issue. All the visualizations can be filtered by date so we are able to follow the question trends along the course.

Figure 3: Dash intentions visualization.

Figure 4: Dash intentions visualization.

7 Discussion

Using Information and Communication technologies in teaching is something that has been going on for a long time. In the last decade, the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) has led to research about how this new technology can be applied to educational settings (Chen et al., 2020). In this scenario, AI has been used in many different areas, including content development, teaching methods, student assessment, and communication between teacher and students (Chassignol et al., 2018). In Chassignol et al., (2018) work, the authors stated that intelligent tutoring systems have been used at different levels of the education system for different subjects in order to track performance and improve the available pedagogical tools.

In programming education, it is common to provide the students with tools that are able to assess if the written code solves the task given by the student, testing the program with different inputs and comparing their outputs with the correct ones (Souza et al., 2016). Tools that encourage students to improve their solution, will improve their learning processes and will motivate them to reach further heights. Through our intelligent tutor it is possible to assess if the students questions are answered correctly, but still some efforts need to be done in order to include some kind of learning assessment. However, AI was successfully used to detect students questions with a high accuracy, allowing the platform to give a good answer with the corresponding examples that will help the students in the understanding of that answer.

Authors such as Rus et al. (Rus et al., 2013), observed that intelligent tutoring systems equipped with conversational and dialogue abilities, have fostered realization of effectiveness in teaching. In this sense, other authors such as Pokrivcakova also observed that the integration of AI and the use of chatbots also improve the learning experiences of students because they leverage machine learning algorithm and deliver content customized to students learning needs and capabilities (Pokrivcakova, 2019), improving this way the learners satisfaction. Although students at first were reluctant to use the intelligent tutor, since they still believe that a human teacher will help them in a better way, they discovered through time that they were able to solve their issues faster, specially when they arose when they were not in the classroom.

TO DO: PARAGRAPH answering RQ with the questionnaire answers

One of the main problems of creating an intelligent tutor, is the amount of information that the models used require in order to provide answers to the people using the application. Our tool focuses only in answering questions related to a certain course. This way, the model size is reduced and can be deployed successfully in a server with a decent GPU. This has allowed us to adapt the intelligent tutor to work with students' questions in different courses. This way, a teacher can easily prepare a new model for his/her course so the chatbot can be set up by the student to work against that model. In this scenario, our intelligent tutor can support teachers in different courses just by preparing the questions, answers and examples related to that course. It would be possible to include all the models in just one deployment, being the student

the one that needs to select the course first so the tutor will answer questions of that course, or it is possible to deploy one tutor for each course, having each tutor access to the model corresponding to that course.

8 Conclusions

In this work we present an intelligent tutor system aimed to support teaching in programming courses. The intelligent tutor uses deep learning algorithms in order to detect students questions and provide answers and examples that help the students. The platform has been used successfully in a programming course with students of Biomedical Engineering at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, showing the potential of incorporating AI in this kind of courses.

Although the students were satisfied with the overall performance of the intelligent tutor, this does not mean that there were no problems. Along the course, the students came up with new questions and new ways of formulating questions that were already implemented in the model. Swift action was needed in those scenarios in order to incorporate new contents to the model. Even if the usage of the tutor threw good results, it still lacks the possibility of automatically assess students' code, which is an area that we are working on.

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